

IMPACT OF INTEGRATED FARMING SYSTEM (IFS) ON DEVELOPMENT OF SCHEDULED CASTE FARMERS IN MYSORE DISTRICT

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Abstract

The study was conducted in purposively selected Mysore district with purposively selected sample of 240 respondents. Data was collected by using pretested structured interview schedule and analysed using appropriate statistical tools. The results revealed that, a majority of the respondents belonged to low category of education level, cropping pattern, livestock possession, innovativeness, mass media exposure, extension participation followed by medium category of cosmopolitanism, training undergone, willingness in agriculture and high category of social participation, level of aspiration and risk orientation. Livelihood security of respondents in 'less satisfied category' decreased to 29.58 per cent from 43.33 per cent and in 'highly satisfied category' increased to 42.08 per cent from 33.75 per cent after implementation of the project. Livestock and crop component generated 295.44 mandays of employment per annum and Rs. 56,066.40 net income to beneficiary farmers. The average gross income of Rs. 83,496.40 from both crop and livestock enterprises of IFS against Rs. 23,632.40 before implementation of the project. As such, for every one rupee investment under IFS they are getting Rs. 3.04 rupee income. The characteristics such as land holding, cropping pattern, livestock possession, cosmopolitanism, innovativeness, mass media exposure, extension participation, level of aspiration, training undergone and willingness in agriculture had positive and significant relationship with livelihood security. The R^2 value indicated that all the 13 independent variables had contributed to the tune of 65.30 per cent of variation in livelihood security of the respondents towards IFS. Hence, the concerned development departments should organize the demonstrations, trainings, field days, exposure visits etc., to educate the resource poor farmers about IFS. The positive and significantly related characteristics need to be considered while selecting the farmers by developmental departments for the extension educational programmes to enhance their livelihood security.

Keywords: Integrated Farming System, Scheduled Caste and Livelihood Security.

Introduction

Agriculture is the most important livelihood option in India, with two third of the country's workforce depending on farming. Majority of them are small and marginal farmers, which has accounted for around 87 per cent of the operational holdings are less than two hectares (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). Increasing land fragmentation, diminishing natural assets, high costs for external farm inputs, indebtedness and pesticide-related health issues have threatened the livelihoods of many farm families. Integration of farm enterprises provides better livelihood in terms of increased food production, higher net income and improved health, habitat, educational and social status. Therefore introduction of appropriate farming systems is going to be one of the important approaches to achieve better growth in agriculture and securing livelihoods of major segment of society. Through Integrated Farming System (IFS) it is possible to reach the high level of productivity in more sustainable way with proportionately less input. The University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore has implemented the project entitled "Livelihood Improvement of Scheduled Caste (SC) Farm Families through Integrated Farming System (IFS)" with the financial support from the Government of Karnataka under Scheduled Caste Sub Plan (SCSP). The project aims at sustainable development of agriculture among the SC farm families by bringing them to mainstream and also efficient management of soil, water, crop and Integrated Pest Management practices in crop husbandry. Further, it integrate dairy, poultry, sheep, piggery, fishery, sericulture, agro-forestry and other related enterprises with crop husbandry which increases the overall net income.

In Karnataka, the Scheduled Caste (SC) population comprised of 17.15 per cent and majority of them belongs to small and marginal farmers and agricultural labourers (Anon, 2018). They are directly or indirectly depend on agriculture for their livelihood. The per capita land holding of SC farmers is 1.3 ha as against state average of 1.74 ha. with fragile resource base, the agricultural production systems of these farmers largely dependent on monsoon, coupled with fragmentation of land

resulted in low production and productivity. They are more exposed to the constant threat of poverty, illiteracy, hunger, starvation, malnutrition and migration to urban areas. Having understood the SC farmers have the potentiality to perform the diversified operations / practices of production systems, integration of appropriate possible number of farming system components out of the available alternatives (crop production, dairy, sheep, piggery, poultry, fisheries sericulture, apiculture, mushroom production, horticulture, agro-forestry, post-harvest and value additions etc.) with due considerations to improve their livelihood is the way out for betterment of SC farmers. With this background, the present study is conceptualized with following objectives:

1. To know the personal, social, economic and psychological characteristics of respondents
2. To measure the livelihood security of SC farmers practicing Integrated Farming System
3. To ascertain the relationship between personal and socio-psychological characteristics of respondents with their livelihood security
4. To know the economic analysis of Integrated Farming System on development of SC farmers

Methodology

The study was conducted in purposively selected Mysore district of Karnataka based on the implementation of the project entitled "Livelihood Improvement of Scheduled Caste (SC) Farm Families through Integrated Farming System (IFS)" by University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore during 2014-15 to 2018-19. A total sample of 240 respondents were purposively selected for the study from two taluks and two grama panchyaths based on maximum number of SC farm families. All the farm families having land holding 1 to 5 acres of dry land were considered as beneficiaries (respondents) under the project. Data was collected using structured pretested interview schedule and analysed using mean, percentage, standard deviation and correlation coefficient.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to their personal, socio-economic and psychological characteristics

(n=240)

Sl. No.	Variables	Category	Number	Per cent
1.	Education level	Low	101	42.08
		Medium	41	17.08
		High	98	40.84
2.	Land holding	Marginal	100	41.66
		Small	90	37.50
		Big	50	20.84
3.	Cropping pattern	Low	86	35.83
		Medium	81	33.75
		High	73	30.42
4.	Livestock possession	Low	91	37.92
		Medium	69	28.75
		High	80	33.33
5.	Cosmopolitaness	Low	62	25.83
		Medium	104	43.33
		High	74	30.84
6.	Innovativeness	Low	103	42.91
		Medium	61	25.41
		High	76	31.68
7.	Mass media exposure	Low	98	40.83
		Medium	51	21.25
		High	91	37.92
8.	Extension Participation	Low	93	38.75
		Medium	58	24.17
		High	89	37.08
9.	Social participation	Low	69	28.75
		Medium	80	33.34
		High	91	37.91
10	Level of aspiration	Low	75	31.25
		Medium	77	32.08
		High	88	36.67
11	Risk orientation	Low	73	30.41
		Medium	75	31.25
		High	92	38.34
12	Training undergone	Low	77	32.08
		Medium	82	34.16
		High	81	33.76
13	Willingness in agriculture	Low	57	23.75
		Medium	141	58.75
		High	42	17.50

The results given in the Table 1 revealed that, a majority of the respondents belonged to low category of education level, cropping pattern, livestock possession, innovativeness, mass media exposure, extension participation followed by medium category of cosmopolitaness, training undergone, willingness in agriculture and high category of social participation, level of aspiration and risk orientation. The possible reason for low category of above mentioned variables could be due to poverty and other social stigma in the rural areas. Respondents found to have low level of education and the land holding distribution is matching with the general trend in the country. About 87 per cent are marginal and small holding and another supporting reason that could be attributed to this trend might be due to

fragmentation of land holding. The ancestral lands were broken into smaller units, due to increase in nuclear families. With respect to low level of mass media exposure and cosmopolitaness, the accessibility to the mass media such as television, radio, newspapers and farm magazines was found to be less. Farmers hardly have the habit of reading newspaper and farm magazines because majority of them had low education level and lack of time and interest in travelling to cities and exposing to mass media as well. They may not listened to radio programmes and watch television for agricultural programmes due to irregular and less power supply in rural areas. The results of the present study are in conformity with the findings of Mamathalakshmi (2013), Harshitha *et al.*, (2018) and Venkatareddy(2021).

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to their Livelihood Security

Category	Before		After		Change in Per cent
	Number	Per cent	Number	Per cent	
Less satisfied	104	43.33	71	29.58	-7.43
Satisfied	55	22.92	68	28.33	2.00
Highly Satisfied	81	33.75	101	42.08	5.42
Total	240	100.00	240	100.00	

A critical appraisal of Table 2 indicated that, livelihood Security of respondents in 'less satisfied category' decreased to 29.58 per cent from 43.33 per cent and in 'highly satisfied category' increased to 42.08 per cent from 33.75 per cent after implementation of the project. The intervention of IFS increased income from both crop cultivation and

animal husbandry, reduced efforts required to dispose of waste, improved soil health, reduced use of chemical fertilizers and cost of production might have contributed for enhancement in livelihood security. The findings seek support from the studies of Sujay Kumar (2018) and Shwetha and Shivalingiah (2019).

Table 19: Dimension-wise impact analysis of livelihood security among respondents

SI. No.	Dimension	Mean Value		Percentage increase
		Before	After	
1	Assets	1138	1676	47.28
2	Living amenities	1202	1704	41.76
3	Economic efficiency	504	816	61.90
4	Ecological security	624	973	55.93
5	Social equitability	588	882	50.00
6	Coping strategies against stress	654	928	41.90
7	Employment security	738	1121	51.90
Overall Livelihood Security		5448	8100	48.68

The data depicted in Table 3 indicated that, the improvement in different dimensions of livelihood security after the implementation of the project. Out of seven dimensions, maximum increase was noticed in economic efficiency (61.90%), ecological security (55.93%), employment security (51.90%), social equitability (50.00%), followed by assets (47.28%), coping strategies against stress

(41.90%) and living amenities (41.76%) and overall livelihood security increased by 48.68 per cent after implementation of the IFS project. Integration of Livestock and Crop component generated extra man days of employment per annum and effective utilization of resources in IFS ensured ecological development in the farming system. The results were supported by the findings of Sujay Kumar (2012).

Table 4: Relationship between personal and socio-psychological characteristics of respondents with their livelihood security

SI. No.	Independent variables	Correlation co-efficient (r)
1.	Education level	0.083 ^{NS}
2.	Land holding	0.193**
3.	Cropping pattern	0.377**
4.	Livestock possession	0.291**
5.	Cosmopolitaness	0.196**
6.	Innovativeness	0.405**
7.	Mass media exposure	0.107**
8.	Extension participation	0.411**
9.	Social participation	-0.004 ^{NS}
10.	Level of aspiration	0.143*
11.	Risk orientation	-0.057 ^{NS}
12.	Training undergone	0.373**
13.	Willingness in agriculture	0.418**

NS: Non-Significant; *: Significant at 5% level; **: Significant at 1% level.

The findings in the Table 4 implied that, 10 out of 13 characteristics found to have significant relationship with livelihood security. The characteristics such as land holding, cropping pattern, livestock possession, cosmopolitaness, innovativeness, mass media exposure, extension participation, level of aspiration, training undergone and willingness in agriculture had positive and significant relationship with

livelihood security. The possible reasons for the positive and significant relationship between land holding and livelihood security might be due to land holding is the major asset which provides economic security to the respondents thereby it leads secured livelihood. Inputs such as seeds and livestock components were provided free of cost to respondents under the project which leads them to get engaged in rearing of

livestock as subsidiary occupation and gets additional income by selling milk and meat apart from crop production. Cropping pattern have positive and significant relationship with livelihood security, as farmers mainly depends on farming, increased in cropping pattern and adopting the new technologies advised by the scientists led to higher productivity, profitability fetching higher income and generated employment. Higher level of mass media exposure could have facilitated the members to develop habits of gathering more information about the improved IFS activities. Level of aspiration and training undergone had positive and significant relationship with livelihood security since the respondents spent more time in IFS to fulfil their

aspirations such as multiple cropping, diary, piggery, sheep rearing and poultry etc. The participation in training programmes enhanced the knowledge about different components of IFS and respondents directly influenced by the training undergone. Regular contact with the project extension personnel, agriculture officers, scientists of agriculture university and hence the respondents might have developed inclination towards IFS. Being an IFS farmer effective utilization of available resources leads to higher productivity, profitability, employment generation, farm income and secured livelihood. The findings are in conformity with the results obtained by Mamathalakshmi (2013), Harshitha *et al.*, (2018) and Venkatareddy(2021).

Table 5: Multiple regression analysis of personal and socio-psychological characteristics of respondents with their livelihood security

(n=240)

Sl. No.	Variables	Regression coefficient (b)	Std. Error of regression co-efficient (SE _b)	't' value
1.	Education level	0.159	0.107	1.485 ^{NS}
2.	Land holding	1.206	0.323	3.736**
3.	Cropping pattern	0.936	0.325	2.883**
4.	Livestock possession	-0.093	0.135	-0.690
5.	Cosmopolitaness	-0.026	0.200	-.129 ^{NS}
6.	Innovativeness	0.117	0.037	3.159**
7.	Mass media exposure	-1.555	0.401	-3.875 ^{NS}
8.	Extension participation	2.114	0.675	3.133**
9.	Social participation	-0.523	0.314	-1.667
10.	Level of aspiration	0.546	0.274	1.993*
11.	Risk orientation	0.057	0.135	0.423 ^{NS}
12.	Training undergone	0.320	0.131	2.450*
13.	Willingness in agriculture	0.131	0.125	1.055 ^{NS}

R² = 0.6530, F = 14.23**; NS: Non-Significant; *: Significant at 5% level; **: Significant at 1% level.

The contribution of independent variables to the livelihood security of the respondents was assessed and illustrated in the Table 5. The findings conveyed those six independent variables such as land holding, cropping pattern, innovativeness, extension participation, level of aspiration, training undergone had contributed significantly to the livelihood security. The remaining variables had not contributed significantly towards variability in livelihood security. The R² value indicated that all the 13 independent variables had contributed to the tune of 65.30 per cent of variation in livelihood security. The possible reason with regard to the extent of contribution of independent variables to variation in livelihood security of the respondents is due to land holding, cropping pattern, innovativeness, extension participation, level of aspiration, training undergone characteristics of respondents were the factors going to influence directly on livelihood security of the respondents. Independent variables have synergic effects to one another, helping each other to have a major extent of contribution towards the livelihood security of farmers. The results of the present study are in conformity with the findings of Harshitha (2018) and Venkatareddy(2021).

The results pertaining to economic analysis of IFS components were presented in the Table 6 indicated that, Livestock and crop component generated 295.44 man days of employment per annum and Rs. 56,066.40 net income to beneficiary farmers. The average gross income of Rs. 83,496.40 from crop and livestock enterprises of IFS against Rs.23,632.40 before implementation of the project. As such, for every one rupee investment under IFS farmers got Rs. 3.04 rupee of income and B:C was found to be enhanced to 3.04 from 2.63. The probable reason for the observed trend is that, Integrated Farming System provided an opportunity to utilize the resources efficiently. Crop diversification, integration of different farming systems provided regular income through the sale of milk, butter / ghee, egg and manure.

Minimum use of off-farm inputs, maximum on-farm inputs and wastes recycling helps to increase and sustain profitability of farm.

Conclusion

Based on the findings it can be concluded that, the results revealed that the livelihood security improved from less satisfied to highly satisfied level, out of seven dimensions of livelihood security maximum increase was noticed in employment security. The characteristics such as land holding, cropping pattern, livestock possession, cosmopolitaness, innovativeness, mass media exposure, extension participation, level of aspiration, training undergone and willingness in agriculture had positive and significant relationship with livelihood security. The findings conveyed that six independent variables such as land holding, cropping pattern, innovativeness, extension participation, level of aspiration, training undergone had contributed significantly to livelihood security. The R² value indicated that all the 13 independent variables had contributed to the tune of 64.40 per cent of variation in livelihood security of the respondents towards IFS. Hence, the concerned development departments should promote and strengthen the IFS activities to enhance the livelihood security of resource poor farmers. The positive and significantly related characteristics needs to be considered while selecting the farmers for IFS programs to enhance their livelihood security.

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Table 20: Economic analysis of Integrated Farming System (IFS) components before and after implementation of project in Mysuru district

(n=240)

Crop Component	Before									After									Change in yield (%)	Change in Income (%)	Emply. Gene. in (Mandays/ac.)	Emply. Gene. of Beneficiary farmers (Mandays)
	Avg. Land Holding (Acre.)	Avg. Yield (Ql./ac.)	Avg. yield of Beneficiary farmers (Ql./ac.)	Price (Rs./Ql.)	Prod. Cost/ac. (Rs.)	Prod. Cost of Beneficiary farmers (Rs.)	Gross Income (Rs./ac.)	Net Income (Rs./ac.)	B:C Ratio	Avg. Yield (Ql./ac.)	Avg. yield of Beneficiary farmers (Ql./ac.)	Price (Rs./Ql.)	Prod. Cost/ac. (Rs.)	Prod. Cost of Beneficiary farmers (Rs.)	Gross Income (Rs./ac.)	Net Income (Rs./ac.)	B:C Ratio					
Paddy	0.82	22.00	18.04	1310.00	6574.00	9000.00	23632.40	14632.40	2.63	26.00	21.32	1520.00	11500.00	9430.00	32406.40	22976.40	3.44	18.18	37.13	92.00	75.44	
Total						9000.00	23632.40	14632.40	2.63					9430.00	32406.40	22976.40	3.44		37.13		75.44	
Livestock Component	Body live wt. or Ltrs/ sheep or poultry or pig or cow		Price/kg or Ltr	Cost		Gross Income (Rs.)	Net Income (Rs.)	B:C Ratio	Body live wt. or Ltrs/ sheep or poultry or pig or cow		Price/kg or Ltr	Cost	Gross Income (Rs.)	Net Income (Rs.)	B:C Ratio	Change in yield (%)	Change in Income (%)	Emply. Gene. (Mandays)	Emply. Gene. of Beneficiary farmers (Mandays)			
Cow (n1=300)									1755.00		28.00	18000.00	49140.00	31140.00	2.73				220.00			
Poultry* (n2=290)									13.00		150.00		1950.00	1950.00								
Total												18000.00	51090.00	33090.00	2.84				220.00			
Grand total				9000.00		23632.40	14632.40	2.63				27430.00	83496.40	56066.40	3.04		37.13		295.44			

* Inter crop